

Separation of Amino Acids from Taramira (*Eruca sativa*) Oilcake

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AMINO acids are important contents of oilseed cakes¹. Various microbiological methods² and colorimetric methods³ have been used for the determination of these amino acids. The rapid ligand exchange chromatography has also been used successfully for the separation of α -amino acids by using metal(II) form of resin such as Chelx-100, Biorex-70 containing carboxylic groups or phosphonic acid groups^{4,5}. The amino acids have been determined in oilcakes by different workers but possibly individuals have not been separated from the hydrolysate of oilcakes. The work on the hydrolysis and determination of amino acids in Taramira oilcake has not been reported in literature. Hence, this work was undertaken. The amino acids were separated by formation of their complexes with transition metal ions using metal form of resin.

Experimental

The residual oil present in the commercial sample of taramira cake, was extracted with *n*-hexane. It was followed by treatment with hot water for 2 h in order to remove the toxic materials³. The sample was hydrolysed in a sealed tube by treating with 6 *N* hydrochloric acid at 110° for 48 h.

The resin Amberlite IR-120 was treated with 1*M* NaOH and 1*M* HCl alternately ten times and washed with deionised water intermittently. Then the resin was treated with 1*M* copper sulphate solution (100 ml) and stirred for 24 h followed by draining off copper sulphate solution and washing off the resin with distilled water until the eluate gave no colour with sodium diethyldithiocarbamate. A glass column (0.9 × 90 cm) was packed with copper(II)-form of the resin upto 60 cm and the resin was equilibrated with 0.1 *N* NH₄OH until the effluent pH was 10.0. It required 8–10 h for equilibration of the column. The sample (10 ml) after adjusting its pH to 10.0 with concentrated NH₄OH was applied to the column. Then the elution was done successively with 0.1, 1, 2 and 3 *N* NH₄OH solutions. The effluent volumes were collected in 5 ml fractions. The flow rate was set to 5 ml in 10 min. The observations were repeated thrice.

The column was treated similarly with the resin containing transition metal ions such as Mn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III} and Zn^{II} to study the effect of metal ions on the elution volume and elution sequence of amino acids present in the taramira oilcake.

Thin layer chromatography was used to identify the amino acids present⁶ by comparing with the standard values.

For the estimation of amino acids, ninhydrin method⁷ was used. The concentrations of amino acids separated from protein hydrolysate were estimated from the standard absorption plots.

Results and Discussion

The active sites in the resin of Amberlite IR-120 are sulphonic acid groups which bind the transition metal ions. The metal ions are retained by the matrix of the resin when dilute ammonia solution (0.1 *N*) is run through it; there is complexation of ammonia with metal ion present in the fixed matrix. On applying the ammoniacal protein hydrolysate to the column, the mixed ligand complexes containing amino acid and ammonia are formed and the amino acids are retained by the fixed matrix depending upon the stability of the complexes whereas the peptides are not retained due to formation of metal chelates. The Ligand exchange equilibria may be represented as

The crude proteinous matter obtained from the taramira oilcake when treated with 6*N* HCl at 110° for 48 h yielded a mixture of amino acids along with peptides. The amino acids present in the hydrolysate were detected by thin layer chromatography. The hydrolysate sample was applied to the column containing Cu^{II}-form of the resin. On applying 0.1 *N* NH₄OH to the column, the peptides metal chelates are eluted in the first 20 ml of the effluent. The amino acids are then eluted depending upon the stability of their metal complexes, by further running successively with 0.1, 1, 2 and 3 *N* NH₄OH solutions. Thin layer chromatography was employed further to confirm the amino acids present in the different fractions of the eluate by running chromatoplates of amino acids present in the elutant along with the possible standard amino acids. One gram of crude protein matter of taramira oilcake yielded the amino acids on successive elution with 0.1, 1, 2 and 3 *N* NH₄OH as shown in Table 1. Taramira oilcake appears to be a good source of glutamic acid, arginine and histidine. The elution sequence of

these amino acids is : glutamic acid > leucine > phenylalanine > tryptophan > arginine > histidine > lysine. Glutamic acid being acidic amino acid, is eluted first, followed by the group of neutral amino acids (leucine, phenylalanine, tryptophan) and the group of basic amino acids (arginine, histidine, lysine). This agrees with the previously reported order for elution of amino acid using the Cu^{II} -form of the resin containing carboxylic acid or phosphonic acid groups⁶.

TABLE 1—YIELD OF AMINO ACIDS FROM TARAMIRA OILCAKE

Amino acid	Percentage Yield (%)	
	Proteinous residue	Raw oilcake
Arginine	9.0	5.94
Glutamic acid	16.5	10.89
Histidine	5.0	3.30
Leucine	2.8	1.84
Lysine	1.2	0.79
Phenylalanine	2.7	1.78
Tryptophan	2.3	1.51

The basic pattern of elution sequence of amino acids with Zn^{II} -form of the resin is the same as that with Cu^{II} -form. In the case of Fe^{III} , the order of the elution sequence is the same except that lysine is eluted before histidine. However, when Mn^{II} and Fe^{II} forms of resin were used in the column, the resin became black on adding the NH_4OH solution. The eluted solution gave a precipitate of metal showing the breaking of metal form of the resin. So Mn^{II} and Fe^{II} cannot be used for the separation.

In case of divalent metal ion, the elution volume is less with Zn^{II} -form of the resin than the Cu^{II} -form. This is in agreement with the fact that the Zn^{II} -amino acid complexes are less stable than the Cu^{II} complexes. The elution volumes in the case of Fe^{III} -form of resin are more than those of Zn^{II} -form while less than Cu^{II} -form of the resin.

The separation with Cu^{II} -form of the resin has been repeated thrice and it showed that the column chromatography technique can be used as a practical tool for the isolation of amino acids from taramira oilcake.

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A Comparative Study of the Efficacies of TLC/FID and Plate-TLC Techniques in the Separation of Phospholipids and Galactolipids

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THE separation of galactolipids from phospholipids, present in authentic standards as well as in cabbage extract, was compared by the use of Chromarod-Iatroscan system (including impregnations with boric acid and oxalic acid) and plate-tlc method (including double development). The results are reported herein.

Experimental

Silica gel Chromarods-S II (Iatron Labs, Japan) were used¹. The lipid standards used (Serdary Research Labs, Canada) were: phosphatidyl ethanolamine (PE), phosphatidylcholine (PC), monogalactosyldiglyceride (MGDG) and digalactosyl diglyceride (DGDG). All organic solvents were redistilled under nitrogen before use.

The air flow rate on the Iatroscan TH-10 Analyser (Iatron Labs, Japan) was 2000 ml min⁻¹, the hydrogen pressure 0.73 kg cm⁻² and the scan speed 2 mm s⁻¹. A Nissci Sangyo Instruments (Japan) model 50 strip chart recorder was used with attenuation of 10 mV and chart speed of 20 cm min⁻¹.

Plate tlc was executed on pre-coated plates (Adsorbosil-5 Prekotes, Applied Science Division, U.S.A.). These were predeveloped with ethyl acetate, activated at 110° for 45 min and then spotted (10 μl of the sample), air-dried, developed, air-dried and then dried at 110°, and finally sprayed with 2', 7'-dichlorofluorescein, concentrated H_2SO_4 , α -naphthol or exposed to iodine vapour.

The cabbage (*Brassica oleracea*) lipids were extracted as described by Peng². The extract was freed from the chlorophyll pigments by passing it through a SEP-PAK silica cartridge (Waters, U.S.A.) and eluting with chloroform³.

Results and Discussion

In the TLC/FID analysis several solvent systems were tried, viz. Me_2CO , $\text{Me}_2\text{CO}-\text{MeOH}$, CHCl_3-